
Pilot report

EM

Expanded Memories: Artistic Experiments into Hybrid Analogue-Digital Film Production

Final Report of FilmEU_RIT Pilot project, 2022-2024

Participating researchers.

Institute of Art, Design and Technology (IADT):

- John Buckley
- Diaa Lagan
- Judith Pernin

Universidade Lusófona (UL):

- Fuad Halwani
- José Carlos Neves
- José Gomez Pinto
- João Salazar Trindade.

LUCA School of Arts:

- Guido Devadder
- Steven Malliet
- Veronika Romhány
- Gert Wastyn

External (Re:ANIMA – Griffith University):

- Thanut Rujitanont

Topic and main objectives.

"Expanded Memories: Artistic Experiments into Hybrid Analogue-Digital Film Production" is an artistic research project aiming to experiment with hybrid forms of analogue-digital (animation) film in order to create objects of tertiary memory. The project targets the following artistic and theoretical goals: (1) to expand the boundaries of the medium by making crossovers to the performative and fine arts; (2) to generate new understandings of audience embodiment, cognition and participation; (3) to develop a co-creative and interdisciplinary artistic research method; and (4) to explore new formats of exhibition and curation beyond the traditional two-dimensional screen.

Guided by insights from media archaeology, philosophy of technology and psychology of embodied cognition we revisited a range of (analogue) production techniques and devices, and remediated these using digital post-production, editing and sequencing methods. This has resulted in a collection of experimental audiovisual works that have been showcased in a hybrid digital-physical way. A digital component has been archived in our shared virtual environment, but a performative and location-specific embedment is required to experience the material, spatial and temporal characteristics of the intended hybridization process.

Multidisciplinary co-creation has been at the heart of this project. Each partner initiated one or more cases based on their ongoing research in expanded (animation) film. In later stages, intermediary prototypes of each case have been (digitally) reinterpreted and/or (mechanically) reproduced by researchers from the other universities. As such, each case did not result in one final output, but in an ongoing series of remediations that reflect the collaborative process, and the research identity and cultural context of each collaborator.

We have exhibited these works on several occasions (cfr. below: OUTPUTS) in a way that not only were the artistic objects themselves showcased, but especially, their continuous history and evolution. As the research combines technical, methodological, theoretical, and artistic concerns, the exhibitions we organized were essentially multimodal: arti-facts have been displayed alongside written reflections (e.g. research papers), audiovisual documentation of the research process, and technical descriptions of the tools and production methods.

Project Outcomes

.consolidate teams inside the clusters;

The co-creative and collaborative method has proven a useful strategy to establish and strengthen connections between the research units of all campuses involved. For instance, there has been an artistic workshop at Lusófona, where José Neves and João Trindade (Lusófona) exchanged technical and artistic expertise with Daa Lagan and John Buckley (IADT), which resulted in the co-creation of hybrid artefacts. Similarly, Daa Lagan (IADT) has visited Belgium to create crossovers with the works of Guido Devadder and Gert Wastyn, and there have been continuous efforts (currently still ongoing) to use virtual spaces to exchange digital artefacts. Also, Lusofóna researchers Natalie Woolf and Lea Vidakovic, and Griffith University researcher Thanut Rujitanont have been invited as keynote speakers at the Nonfiction Animation and Memory Exposium organized by Guido Devadder in December 2023.

The collaborative processes have been monitored by Veronika Romhányi, with Steven Malliet, as these processes make up the focus of her Ph.D. research. Part of what made this project fun and interesting is that we had an organic and authentic way of working together.

.artistic practice-led research

Artistic research makes up the core of this project: experimental, iterative creation of animation artefacts, in an inter-disciplinary dialogue with fellow researchers. We believe that the expositions we have done so far, showcase interesting ways of communicating about research that is predominantly practice-led: for instance, there was a poster, with a presentation at the Cumulus conference, which ran simultaneously with a 3-day exposition at the Royal Academy of Fine Arts in Antwerp.

In one of the research papers that were produced about the project (cfr. Appendix 2) we describe the artistic research method as follows: *“Artistic research is a relatively young but fast-growing methodology that attracts an increasing number of researchers and scholars. It places artistic creation at the heart of the investigative process and as such it is akin to practical research that has a long tradition within, for instance, engineering (Coessens et al. 2009). It is, however, different from applied research in the sense that it embraces the unexpected, often intuitive nature of the artistic process, which can lead to unpredicted research outcomes (Raami 2015; Coessens et al. 2009). An essential part of artistic research is that it generates so-called tacit knowledge: knowledge that cannot be merely captured in written form but is contained within the artistic works that are created and can be understood as such by peers and fellow practitioners (Borgdorff 2010). Nonetheless, the creation of theoretical knowledge is highly relevant in artistic research: the artist-researcher uses theoretical knowledge to inform, inspire, and critically evaluate their practice, thereby becoming what Donald Schön referred to as a reflective practitioner (Schön 1983). Because of its fluid and experimental nature, artistic research is highly suitable to generate interpretive, nonlinear, and immersive insights into personal and communal discourses, complementing the results of existing qualitative and quantitative methods of inquiry (Sullivan 2009).”* (Malliet et.al, 2024, in press).

.R&I Resources and Strategic Agenda

Expanded Memories is an interdisciplinary and interinstitutional collaboration taking place between the various artists and researchers part of the group. Hailing from 3 different HEIs located in Ireland, Portugal and Belgium, these artists and researchers are experts in fields ranging from fine arts, animation and game design to communication and philosophy, and are at different career stages (from researchers on

a PhD trajectory to PhD candidates, to senior researchers). From the outset, the inter-human collaboration was conducted on a fairly equal footing, despite the discrepancy in career stages among the group members. PhD candidates were particularly active in exchanging their knowledge with each other and took a leading role in fostering interdisciplinary and interinstitutional collaboration, under the guidance of the Project coordinator and with the assistance of each HEIs involved. While our individual roles in the project were clear from the start, spontaneous collaborations between the researchers and the 3 HEIs were made possible thanks to a flexible communication style and non-hierarchical structure of the group. This led to both creative and research activities beyond the group members' fields of expertise and also helped with reporting purposes. As a collective, the group took part organically in reporting activities when they were communicated to us by the FilmEU_RIT coordinators through the FilmEU_RIT channels. While the LUCA project coordinator took the lead with reporting, one or more group members from each HEI was also informally chosen to be the person in charge of internal coordination and reporting duties. If there were at times uncertainties about administrative and organizational issues – namely, budget allocation and management, instruction on reporting requirements, participation in summits – they were quickly addressed by the FilmEU_RIT coordinators and easily responded to the Expanded Memories collective.

The project showcases the innovative potential of Artistic Research as a social-cultural force and an academic, epistemological approach that is rapidly gaining recognition. The research has been practice-led in the sense that (collaborative) artistic experimentation has constituted the core of our endeavors.

First, the artistic objects we have created can be considered as carriers of multidisciplinary knowledge: they could not have been developed in this form if it were not for the exchange of expertise between different media and approaches. For instance, José Neves' expertise in building mechanical installations, comprising basic interaction rules, permeates all artefacts that have been created, just like Guido Devadder's extensive knowledge on constructing media-archaeological installations. The concept of working with shadow casting as an innovative practice for spatial animation, was developed through the dialogue between John Buckley/Diaa Lagan Dreamachine, José Neves Shadow Machine and Guido Devadder's experiments with anamorphosis, and connected well to the research of José Pinto on shadow art and reality vs. absence of reality. As described above, we organized several workshops (in Lisbon, at LUCA –with also Re:ANIMA students participating- and in Dublin at the FimEU summit) where several of the participating researchers shared their expertise and exchanged practical methods. As is described in for instance the paper

by Wastyn et al. (Appendix 3) this exchange of expertise has been crucial for each subproject that the research consisted of. In this sense, Expanded Memories has provided all researchers not only with a co-creative artistic experience, but also with a learning experience, enriching their practice with insights from Interaction Design, Philosophy, Game Design, visual art.

Second, the works we created and exhibited can be considered as cultural artefacts that engage in a cross-cultural dialogue with one another. For instance, the input of Diaa Lagan and Fuad Halwani enriched the works with inspirations from Middle Eastern intellectual and artistic traditions (cfr. Malliet et al., 2024, Appendix 2), and this dimension was fortified by opening our models, practices and documents to the students of the second intake of the Re:ANIMA MA program, who re-interpreted the artefacts, for instance by referencing the “Women, Life, Freedom” movement. Additionally, the inclusion of the works of Thanut Rujitanont in the Antwerp and Brussels expos opened new views on temporality, space, and how these can be related to the processes of memory. The fact that we have been able to exhibit these works on several occasions, demonstrates a fundamental strength of artistic research: we could observe that participants engaged directly with the works, which made them reflect not only about the fundamentals of the animated language, but also about the social-cultural dialogue we aimed to initiate. In the next iteration of Expanded Memories (cfr. below) we aim to have an even stronger focus on this social-cultural-educational dimension of the project.

Third, the research has enabled us to establish strong strategic relations between the 3 universities involved. This manifests itself informally (we have a very amicable relationship with one another, which results in many informal talks where we initiate new ideas for future collaborations) but also formally. For instance, the PLURINARTS MSCDN application that is currently in preparation (to be submitted November 2024) includes researchers from Lusofónia and IADT, focusing on expanding the boundaries of audiovisual art, and therefore builds on the network and insights gained from Expanded Memories. Similarly, this collaboration has led to the invitation of Lusofona researcher Natalie Woolf, (who will join our collective in the next iteration), as keynote speaker at the Exposium on Nonfiction Animation and Memory at LUCA Brussels, and as workshop lecturer in the LUCA semester of Re:ANIMA. In several of the Ph.D. projects that have contributed to this research (e.g. Gert Wastyn, Veronika Romhány) researchers from the partner universities have been included in the doctoral committee because of the connections made in this project. In short, since our collaborations have proceeded in both a very friendly and professional way, we are convinced that future collaborations will continue to emerge in an authentic and organic way.

One case that demonstrates the versatile nature and the various collaborative dimensions of the project, is the exhibition that we did at the Method Meets Art expo in Antwerp, which ran alongside the Cumulus conference, hosted by the University of Antwerp in April 2023. We had at our disposal a large exposition space, which enabled us to expose early versions of almost all artefacts that had been created at that point and put them in a dialogue with one another within the spatial context. Small objects were juxtaposed to large video mappings of the same visuals, complemented with a corner that allowed participants to experience some of the works in VR. At the entrance of the expo, we showcased a digital poster that explained the theoretical foundations of the research, which were elaborated further in a 30-minute presentation that Steven Malliet gave at the Cumulus venue in the same building. This presentation plus poster, alongside the feedback we received from our peers, formed the basis for the academic paper we later wrote, and which has currently been accepted in Animation Studies journal. The expo was set up by several researchers, whereby collaborators from IADT and UL joined the LUCA researchers. Setting up the expo together entailed explaining to each other the technical and artistic qualities of each work, and demonstrated that it was necessary to combine our different expertises to make such a multidisciplinary effort possible. The lessons learned from putting our works together in the same artistic space, and observing the impact of this collective expo on the participants, also laid the foundations for the next iteration of Expanded Memories (cfr. below).

.proof-of-concept instruments and communication platforms used.

On the conceptual level, the collaborative methods and processes are being documented in the context of Veronika Romhányi's Ph.D. project. On a technical level, the models for 3D prints, strobelight installations and VR experiences are made available in an open-source philosophy so that they can be reproduced at other campuses or by different collaborators.

The team essentially used 3 management/collaboration tools: Teams, Discord and Google Docs. Teams worked as a file repository, including work files (e.g. image collection for project presentations, texts, etc.) and final documents such as reports and papers. As a general communication tool, we used the Discord platform subdivided into 3 main areas: organization (general, who-is-who. Meetings, timeline, expo-planning, events and actions, report), research (calls, referrals, state of the art) and Cases-interaction (one area for each of the 5 artworks developed). Each of these areas then functioned as a thematic

subdivision for sharing and collecting ideas on various subjects. Discord was also used for group video conferences which, on average, took place every two weeks throughout the project, but were more frequent when there was an event in progress (e.g. exhibition, paper delivery). Finally, Google Docs was used as a collaborative tool for writing texts because it was the one everyone was already familiar with. The combination of these three tools served the needs of the project without any major repairs.

--- OUTPUTS ----

// Artistic Works ¹

Shadow Machine — Universidade Lusófona; João Trindade, José Carlos Neves, José Gomes Pinto.

Kalam-Machine (كلام, talk) – IADT & Universidade Lusófona; Dīaa Lagan, José Carlos Neves.

Dream-o-trope — LUCA & IADT; Dīaa Lagan and Guido De Vadder.

Lighthouse walk: projection zoetrope — LUCA; Guido De Vadder.

Anamorphotrope —LUCA; Gert Wastyn

Dreammachine — IADT; Dīaa Lagan and John Buckley.

The Announced Tragedy: experimental short film + interactive installation; Thanut Rujitanont

//Expositions:

Re:ANIMA workshop and Expo: Expanded Memories, 4 November 2022, LUCA School of Arts, Genk BE.

Stop-Start Motion: Expanded Animation in Contemporary Art, 30 November – 22 December 2022, LUCA School of Arts, Genk BE.

Method Meets Art Expo, 12-15 April 2023, Royal Academy of Art, Antwerp BE.

The Lab Gallery, 5 September – 4 December 2023, Dublin IR.

INSHADOW Lisbon Screendance Festival, 20 November – 15 December 2023, Lisbon PT.

Nonfiction Animation and Memory Exposium, 8 December 2023, Brussels BE.

//Presentations at international conferences and symposia²:

Malliet, S., Buckley, J., Devadder, G., Lagan, D., Neves, J., Pernin, J., Pinto, J., Romhány, V., Rujitanont, T., Salazar Trindade, J., & Wastyn, G. (2023). Expanded memories: artistic experiments into hybrid analogue-digital film production. Poster + Presentation presented at *Cumulus 2023: Connectivity and Creativity in times of Conflict*, Antwerp, 2023/04/15.

Malliet, S., Romhány, V. (2023). Expanded Memories: Artistic Research within a Horizon Europe context. *Presented at the Vitality Symposium 2023: supporting the CCI ecosystem of Bulgaria*, Sofia, 16 Mar 2023.

Malliet, S., Buckley, J., Devadder, G., Lagan, D., Lesmes Lopez, C.E., Neves, J., Pernin, J., Pinto, J., Romhány, V., Salazar, J., Wastyn, G. (2022). Expanded Memories: Artistic Experimentations into Hybrid Digital/Analogue Animation Styles. Presented at the *DigiSoc Unconference: Exchanges on Media & Culture*, BAC Art Lab, Leuven, 22 Sep 2022-22 Sep 2022.

//Academic Papers³

Published:

Malliet, S., Buckley, J., Devadder, G., Lagan, D., Neves, J., Pernin, J., Pinto, J., Romhány, V., Rujitanont, T., Salazar Trindade, J., Wastyn, G. (2024). Expanded memories: artistic experiments into hybrid analogue-digital film production. *Animation Studies*, 19. <https://journal.animationstudies.org/steven-malliet-john-buckley-guido-devadder-et-al-expanded-memories-artistic-experiments-into-hybrid-analogue-digital-animation/>

Under review:

Wastyn, G., Malliet, S., Devadder, G., Geerts, B. (2024). Artistic Experiments in Expanded Animation: Combining 3D Printing with Virtual Reality to Create Anamorphic Shadow Animations. Submitted for review at International Journal on Stereo & Immersive Media (IJSIM).

Ji, X., Malliet, S., Muravevskaia, E. (2024). Promoting Empathy through the Design of an Embodied Installation Game. Submitted for review at International Journal on Stereo & Immersive Media (IJSIM).

.theoretical and conceptual contributions

On the theoretical level the project has contributed to an enhanced understanding of the connection between animation and memory, through exploration of the possibilities of the Expanded Animation medium. An elaborate discussion of this can be found in Malliet et. al. (2024, upcoming). Following quote from this paper illustrates the way in which the versatile and heterogeneous constitution of our team has resulted in an understanding of this topic that combines media theory, philosophy of technology and cultural studies:

“Animation has a long history of dealing with topics of cognition and memory, for instance through the use of nonlinear associative storytelling (e.g., Yuri Norstein’s Skazka Skazok/Tale of Tales), by recreating the history of certain places or cultures (e.g., Vuc Jevremovic’s Patience of the Memory) or by recounting instances of individual or collective trauma (e.g., Ülo Pikkov’s Body Memory). A comprehensive overview of the different ways in which animation can be considered as a performative practice enacting the processes of recounting and remembering can be found in the introduction of van Gageldonk et al.’s book on the subject (2020). Animation films often deal with remembering, forgetting, or dreaming, and make frequent use of visualization methods that represent these processes. Animation is particularly suitable for this, as it incorporates cinematographic techniques that are less intuitive to other media: nonlinear and fragmented time (e.g. Satoshi Kons’s Paprika), muted or fluid colors (e.g., Studio Ghibli’s The Tale of the Princess) or distortion (e.g., Richard Linklater’s Waking Life). In several respects, animation can be considered more ‘irrational’ and ‘incomplete’ than other narrative art forms, and in that sense, it is interestingly related to human cognition (Walden 2018).

Paul Wells (1998) identifies several ways in which animation is connected to memory. From a historic point of view, animation films often function as documents that capture the essence of a time or place. Psychologically, animation has the potential to evoke feelings of nostalgia and activate the long-term memory in powerful ways. Related to this is the observation that animation often relies upon shared symbols that define a group or society, representing what Carl Jung refers to as its collective subconscious. As animated films are often rooted in mythology, folklore, or legends, it can even be argued that animation serves to archive and materialize these shared stories, preserving them for future generations. Finally, still according to Wells (1998), on the semantic level, the language of animation—specifically its ability to morph, transform, and visualize the intangible—makes it highly suitable to represent or mimic the processes of memory, dreams, and thought: “Animation is especially suited to the process of associative linking, both as a methodology by which to create image systems, and as a mechanism by which to understand them” (Wells 1998, 94).

Elaborating on this last point, Dan Torre (2017) describes a number of additional characteristics that set animation apart from other time-based audiovisual media: it is fluid, volatile, rooted in imagination, and open to exaggeration and decontextualization. Animation is deeply connected with human cognition because it reflects, but in its turn also impacts, our ways of thinking, triggering strong mental responses. The specific techniques that animation uses to organize space and time, according to Torre, can be linked to how our mind stores, processes, and retrieves information: “many of the processes of animation and, in fact, the very concept of animation is a basic and natural extension of our real-world experiences” (Torre 2017, 103). Animated works can easily capture ephemeral moments, thoughts, or feelings, giving them a manifestation in a physical or digital medium. Finally, Torre also draws upon Jungian psychoanalysis, positing that animation often taps into universal themes, archetypes, and symbols that have the potential to resonate deeply. When we witness these symbols and themes in animation, they reinforce our understanding and memory of them, creating a cultural feedback loop that strengthens our collective memory.”

In a similar line, the paper of Wastyn, Malliet, Devadder & Geerts (2024) focuses on the artistic principles underlying the shadow casting techniques that constitute a common thread in all the art works that were created:

“Anamorphic art is a visual art form within which a presented image reveals distorted or oblique perspectives, relative to the physical position taken by the spectator, and thus putting the spectator and the work in a spatial interaction with one another (Pagliano, 2024). An anamorphic work can usually be appreciated in its conventional proportions if the viewer assumes a precise point of view that unifies the image’s perspective lines - but interesting artistic possibilities arise when the viewer moves away from this ‘vantage point’ so that additional visual layers are revealed (Pratt et al., 2023). This includes perspective manipulation and geometrical transformations to produce images that look misshapen or elongated when seen from certain points of view. While principles of anamorphosis are often employed to create optical illusions, its artistic use has been explored by surrealist artists (recognizing its potential for creating a sense of alienation or decontextualization) or installation artists (recognizing its potential for intuitive spectator interaction). Historically, the technique can be traced back to examples as far as the Renaissance. Anamorphism has been used in painting, sculpture, and digital art and has been revisited, investigated and experimented with by several contemporary artists. An extensive overview of the history of anamorphosis and its contemporary workings can be found in Knoops (2017).

Artists like Istvan Orosz and Salvador Dali have applied anamorphosis to optical art, creating works that seem abstract or out of proportion unless they are reflected in a cylindrical mirror placed on top or next to them (e.g. Collins, 1992; Turkmen, 2017). Noteworthy in the context of the current project is the use of anamorphosis to create a spatial experience around the projection of an animated video, for instance in the film 'What Will Come (has already come)' by William Kentridge (2007) (Knoops, 2017). In this work, an original, distorted animated film, projected on a round rotating surface, is corrected by a cylindrical mirror placed in the middle of this surface, within which the spectator can experience it as a conventional sequence. The spectator becomes an active participant in observing either the distorted or the corrected image, or both simultaneously. The viewer of an anamorphic work is often referred to as an 'eccentric observer', who has to make an idiosyncratic effort to decipher and de/reconstruct the presented image (Collins, 1992; Knoops, 2017).

A specific form of anamorphic art is anamorphic shadow installation art, where the intended shape is revealed by a projected shadow, created by placing a light source at a specific angle or perspective (Pagliano, 2024). The observer, though not actively needed to create the image by assuming a suitable position, is invited to separate or

juxtapose the physical installation (usually in a disproportional form) and the shadow projection (usually in a conventional form). The volatile yet clear shape of the shadow, in contrast to the distorted materiality of the object, creates a tension that is reflective of our perceptions of the world that surrounds us, specifically raising questions about realism and non-realism (Symeonidou, 2016)."

The future of Expanded Memories:

While we continue to work as an art collective, keeping on board all researchers who have been involved in the past two years, we are also 'expanding' the project, to include additional researchers from:

- LUCA School of Arts: Ada Güvenir, Olivia Ji, Vera Verhoef;
- Universidade Lusófona: Natalie Woolf, João Carrilho;
- National Academy for Theatre and Film Arts (NATFA): Ralitsa Assenova;
- VIA University College: Martina Scarpelli, Lana Tankosa Nikolic;
- University of Bucharest: Mirona Radu.

Based on the expertise of our new members, the next iteration of Expanded Memories will have a more specific focus on the exhibition and juxtaposition of these hybrid animation artifacts in a spatial and/or educational context. Expanded Memories 2.0. will explore the placement-in-context of our works, to discover new spatial (virtual and digital) ways of documenting the collaborative process. One interesting route for this can be found in the format of the *Installation Game*, a central focus of the Ph.D. research of Olivia Ji, which has recently been started at LUCA School of Arts. In a paper on this hybrid art form, we describe the multi-modal (including sound, touch, smell) and interactive nature of this art form, indicating a direction for our future endeavors:

"These hybrid art forms question the boundaries between art disciplines and encourage players to reflect upon their relationship with technology, or with the world that surrounds them. The notion of embodied experience is an essential aspect of the interactions provided by installation games: players are immersed in a multi-sensorial and context-specific relationship with a work, as a result of which they can be provided with a rich or deep understanding of a certain topic or message. [...] In order to achieve such a reflective experience, installation games often implement one specific, embodied, interaction, which symbolizes or enlarges a wider subject or

concern. In their use of minimalistic mechanics, embodied installation games can also be described as experimental games: games that explore new or unconventional modes of interaction; or avant-garde games: games that push the boundaries of what can be considered a game. Especially the recent emergence of critical design has attributed them with strong critical or even radical quality. By addressing a social, psychological or political subject in a non-conventional way, they confront the player with controversial topics that are not always easy to discuss in a linear or narrative fashion. ... “ (Ji, Malliet & Muravevskaia, 2024).

In this way, we expect the input of our new members to open the artistic and social-cultural dimensions of the project, while maintaining our focus on processes of cognition and memory in relation to the boundaries of the animated medium.

REFERENCES

Borgdorff, Henk. *The Production of Knowledge in Artistic Research*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group, 2010.

Coessens, K., D. Crispin, and A. Douglas. *The Artistic Turn: A Manifesto*. Orpheus Instituut; Leuven, Belgium, 2009.

Collins, D. L. (1992). Anamorphosis and the Eccentric Observer: Inverted Perspective and Construction of the Gaze. *Leonardo*, 25(1), 73. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1575625>

Knoops, R. (2015). Cylindrical Anamorphosis. *Thaumaturgical Origins and Contemporary Workings*. 14, 211–225.

Pagliano, A. (2024). Shadow Anamorphic art. In *The urban book series* (pp. 55–71). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-47246-6_6

Pratt, L., Johnston, A. E., & Pietroni, N. (2023). Bending the light: Next generation anamorphic sculptures. *Computers & Graphics*, 114, 210–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cag.2023.05.023>

Raami, Asta. *Intuition Unleashed: On the Application and Development of Intuition in the Creative Process*. Aalto University Press, 2016.

Schön, Donald A. *The Reflective Practitioner: How Professionals Think in Action*. Temple Smith, 1992.

Sullivan, Anne. "Animating Flames: Recovering Fire-Gazing as a Moving-Image Technology." 19: Interdisciplinary Studies in the Long Nineteenth Century, no. 25, Dec. 2017, doi:10.16995/ntn.792.

Symeonidou, I. (2016). Anamorphic Experiences in 3D Space: Shadows, Projections and Other Optical Illusions. Nexus Network Journal, 18(3), 779–797. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00004-016-0298-4>

Torre, Dan. Animation – Process, Cognition and Actuality. Bloomsbury Academic, 2017.

Turkmen, B. B. (2017). Fictional Illustration Language with Reference to M. C. Escher and Istvan Orosz Examples. New Trends And Issues Proceedings On Humanities And Social Sciences, 4(11), 156–163. <https://doi.org/10.18844/prosoc.v4i11.2870>

van Gageldonk, Maarten, László Munteán, and Ali Shobeiri, editors. Animation and Memory. Springer International Publishing, 2020. doi:10.1007/978-3-030-34888-5. Waking Life. Dir. Richard Linklater. Independent Film Channel Productions - Thousand Words - Flat Black Films - Detour Filmproduction, 2001.

Walden, Victoria G. "Animation and Memory." The Animation Studies Reader, edited by Nichola Dobson, 2028, pp. 81-90. [gle Docs](#).

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.